

D7.1. RHODAS Kick-off meeting report

Reinventing High-performance pOwer converters for heavy-Duty electric trAnSport

Grant Agreement Number 101056896

Deliverable name: D7.1. RHODAS Kick-off Meeting report
Deliverable number: 7.1
Deliverable type: Report
Work Package: WP7, Project management and coordination
Lead beneficiary: UPC
Contact person: Luis Romeral (luis.romeral@upc.edu)
Dissemination Level: Public
Due date for deliverable: May 31, 2022

Funded by the
European Union

DOCUMENT CONTROL PAGE

Author(s):	Laura Sanz / Luis Romeral
Contributor(s):	All partners
Reviewer(s):	All partners
Version number:	v.3
Contractual delivery date:	31-05-2022
Actual delivery date:	19-07-2022
Modified by:	Luis Romeral
Status:	Final

REVISION HISTORY

Version	Date	Author/Reviewer	Notes
v.0	24-05-2022	Laura Sanz / NION	Creation
v.1	30-05-2022	Luis Romeral / UPC	Updates and completion Final version, Review 1 by PO
v.2	10-07-2022	Luis Romeral / UPC	Final version, Review 2 by PO
v.3	13-07-2022	Luis Romeral / UPC Jose Saez / NION	Final version, Review by PO
v.4	19-07-2022	Luis Romeral / UPC Jose Saez / NION	Formal corrections Final version submitted

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work described in this publication was subsidised by Horizon Europe (HORIZON) framework through the Grant Agreement Number 101056896.

DISCLAIMER

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

DOCUMENT CONTROL PAGE.....	2
REVISION HISTORY	2
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	2
DISCLAIMER	2
TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	3
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
1. INTRODUCTION.....	6
1.1 DESCRIPTION OF THE DOCUMENT AND PURSUE	6
1.2 WPS AND TASKS RELATED WITH THE DELIVERABLE	6
2. MEETING AGENDA.....	7
2.1 PARTICIPANTS.....	9
2.2 PRESENTATIONS.....	10
2.3 MEETING NOTES	13
2.4 PICTURES OF THE EVENT.....	14
3. THE RHODaS PROJECT.....	20
3.1 CONCEPT	20
3.2 PROJECT SCOPE.....	20
3.3 PROJECT OBJECTIVES.....	21
3.4 PROJECT IMPACT.....	23
3.4.1 TECHNOLOGICAL IMPACT.....	23
3.4.2 ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT.....	25
4. RHODaS WORK PLAN.....	27
4.1 PROJECT WORK PLANS	27

4.2	PROJECT GANTT CHART	30
4.3	RISK REGISTER	31
5.	MANAGEMENT STRUCTURE	34
5.1	PROJECT GOVERNANCE	34
5.1.1	THE PROJECT COORDINATION TEAM	34
5.1.2	THE PROJECT EXECUTIVE BOARD	35
5.1.3	THE SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL COMMITTEE.....	36
5.1.4	PROJECT COORDINATION AND ADMINISTRATIVE MGMT	37
5.1.5	TECHNICAL MANAGEMENT	37
5.1.6	COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION MANAGERS	38
5.1.7	ADVISORY BOARD.....	40
5.2	QUALITY ASSURANCE PLAN (QAP) & PEER REVIEWING.....	41
5.3	PROJECT MEETINGS STRUCTURE.....	42
5.4	DECISION-MAKING	44
6.	COMMUNICATION	45
6.1	PARTNER CONTACT DETAILS.....	46
7.	CONCLUSION	47

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report describes the RHODAS kick-off meeting, including the agenda, the participants, the meeting notes, the relevant parts of the presentations and the group pictures. The event was celebrated at UPC facilities (Edifici Vèrtex) in Barcelona (Spain) during May 19th and 20th. Representatives from each beneficiary entity attended the meeting physically, while online connection was enabled for those participating remotely.

The report also provides information on the governance structure agreed by the consortium to ensure successful implementation of the RHODaS project. This will be achieved by creating governing bodies charged with the responsibility for specific tasks which upon execution will seamlessly integrate with the directives of fellow governing bodies.

Integral to the success of an applied hierarchy of project governance are the defined channels for communication ensuring requisite information to the project partners as and when it is required. The bidirectional nature of the communication flow (bottom-up and top-down) will be realized through appropriate use of meetings, emails, video-conferences and teleconferences. Legal documents, if necessary, will be notarized.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 DESCRIPTION OF THE DOCUMENT AND PURSUE

This report describes the RHODAS kick-off meeting agenda, minutes, participants and parts of the presentations and group pictures. The Meeting has been celebrated in Barcelona (Spain) during May 19th – 20th, in UPC facilities.

The report also includes information on the governance structure agreed by the consortium to ensure successful implementation of the RHODaS project.

1.2 WPS AND TASKS RELATED WITH THE DELIVERABLE

This deliverable refers to Task 7.1 and Task 7.2 included in WP7: Project Management and Coordination.

2. MEETING AGENDA

Day 1: 19th May 2022

- **9:00- 9:30** **Welcome and acknowledgements**
Introduction and welcome from the RHODaS Project Coordinator, Luis Romeral. Acknowledgements from UPC representatives.

- **9:30- 11:00** **Partners introduction**
Corporative presentation of the beneficiary entities, representatives and teams. Please, prepare your presentation supported by some slides.

- **11:00- 11:30** **Coffee break**

- **11:30- 12:00** **RHODaS: General Overview**
Presentation of objectives, impacts, workplan and risks (Project Coordinator)

- **12:00- 13:00** **Introduction and guidelines from the Project Officer: Joao Miranda**

- **13:00- 14:00** **Lunch break**

- **14:00- 17:00** **Technical WPs discussion**
Presentation of work packages by WP Leaders including objectives, description of tasks, milestones and deliverables.

- **17:00- 20:00** **Free time to visit [Barcelona](#)**

- **20:00** **RHODaS Welcome Dinner at [El Jardí de L'Abadessa](#)**
[Carrer de l'Abadessa Olzet, 26, 08034 Barcelona](#)

All the participants are invited to the dinner by the PC (UPC)

Day 2: 20th May 2022

- 9:00- 9:30 **Reception and welcome coffee**

- 9:30- 10:00 **WP7: Project Coordination**
Presentation of WP7 by the Coordination Team Leaders.
Luis Romeral

- 10:00-10:45 **Administrative and financial issues**
Discussion of administrative and financial activities. Q&A session to clarify doubts.
Belén Calejo

- 10:45- 11:15 **Coffee break**

- 11:15- 13:00 **Parallel discussions**
Presentation of WP1 planning and organisation of activities by WPL (VALEO).
Stéphane Aubin and Arame Diop

- 13:00- 14:00 **Lunch break**

2.1 PARTICIPANTS

Name	Entity	Attendance
Luis Romeral	UPC	
Mònica Altimira	UPC	
Alejandro Paredes	UPC	
Diego Arcos	UPC	
Belén Calejo	UPC	
Cristina Barragán	KNEIA	
Ciro Avolio	KNEIA	
Mara Mennella	KNEIA	
Rainer Pamminger	TUW	
Corneliu Barbu	AU	
Rebin Jaber	AIT	
Markus Koller	AIT	
AIT	AIT	
AIT	AIT	
Peter Scheuermann	AIT	Online
Piotr Bielaczyc	BOSMAL	
Arame DIOP	VALEO	
Christophe VERDOUCQ	VALEO	
Stéphane AUBIN	VALEO	
Dirk Bauer	VALEO SIEMENS	
Laura Sanz	NION	
Xavier Llauradó	NION	
Mayte Páez	NION	Online
Joao Miranda	Project Officer	Online

2.2 PRESENTATIONS

After the introduction and welcome from the Coordination Team, led by the Project Coordinator Prof. Luis Romeral, each beneficiary presented the corporate information of the entity and participant teams. These presentations are made available at the shared workspace.

Next, the Project Coordinator Prof. Luis Romeral presented the general overview of the project, including the objectives, impacts, workplan and main risks.

The slides presented are the following:

1

2

3

4

Objectives		RHODAS	
TO1: Improve efficiency and performance of power converters while increasing affordability of powertrains for heavy-duty EVs WPs			
TO1.1	Develop disruptive T-type multilevel converter topologies based on hybrid fault tolerant SiC-GaN DC/DC-AC architectures for high-voltage (2100V), being the target (2200V) traction power trains, allowing more efficient and power dense power electronic converters (about 150 kW per axle, peak efficiency >98%), and reducing the complexity of the controls.	WP2	
TO1.2	Develop new adaptive switching frequency control approaches to further improve the efficiency according to the driving mode, by taking advantage of the WBG wide frequency range (50 kHz-100 kHz for high power converters). Total power losses reduction >40% and EMI reduction is expected by adapting the devices' switching to the torque-speed operating point.	WP2	
TO1.3	Develop novel power converter control strategies with self-learning and intelligent monitoring capabilities, suitable for very high-frequency operation, and fault detection and mitigation through Fault Tolerant Control.	WP2	
TO1.4	Develop a more effective hybrid thermal management system (TMS) of the IMD combining liquid-cooling and air-cooling to mitigate negative effects of high current on health and ageing of the materials and components.	WP3	
KPIs: 40% reduction of thermal losses, temperature operation up to 175°C- truck driving range +10%			
TO2: Reduce size and weight of the power converters WPs			
TO2.1	Effective application of WBG semiconductor materials in a hybrid configuration to boost performance using the minimum amount of material.	WP2	
TO2.2	Develop and fabricate highly integrated base modules for modular power electronics using 3D design and simulation.	WP2	
TO2.3	Achieve compact integration of gate drivers in high-frequency power modules with minimum interferences.	WP2	
KPIs: 50% reduction of size, 30% reduction of weight, 15 dB reduction of EMI noise			

RHODAS KoM 19-20 May 2022

5

Objectives		RHODAS	
TO3: Effective application of digital technologies and sensors for advanced on-line monitoring and intelligent estimation and prediction of states based in advanced modelling and prediction techniques using Big Data Analysis and AI WPs			
TO3.1	Design effective sensor networks able to detect changes in relevant parameters at material, component and system level to provide more accurate models for characterisation and control.	WP3	
TO3.2	Develop an efficient service layer by creating a new software architecture in the cloud (IoT platform) including data acquisition, storage, processing and visualization.	WP4	
TO3.3	Develop and integrate advanced physics and data-driven models in a complete Digital Twin using data provided by the sensor networks. These models are updated in real-time by applying AI and ML techniques.	WP4	
TO3.4	Integration of new smart functionalities, such as state estimation and prediction of materials components and systems.	WP4	
TO3.5	Implement AI based predictive maintenance functionalities and health management strategies for optimising operation, cost and lifecycle of the materials, components and systems, including power train fault tolerant control.	WP4	
KPIs: 30% reduction of failures, 20% reduction of costs, 25% extension of lifetime			
TO4: Effective integration of the power electronics and TMS in a modular and compact IMD to evaluate the overall performance in a complete e-axle test bench WPs			
TO4.1	Validate the operation and performance of the new power converters in a complete system under a wide range of operating conditions, following Automotive quality and safety standards.	WP5	
TO4.2	Create, optimise and update the holistic model of the complete powertrain, including materials, components and systems, to validate accuracy of the digital twin and its functionalities.	WP4WP5	
TO4.3	Validate the fault tolerance operation of the power converters on a complete e-axle testbench.	WP5	
KPIs: Increase total IMD efficiency in more than 5%; Predict converter RUL with accuracy >75%; Reduction of converter losses by 75% over a driving cycle.			

RHODAS KoM 19-20 May 2022

6

Objectives		RHODAS	
TO5: Integration of ecodesign, material criticality and circularity considerations into the RHODAS powertrain solution, as well as viable circular business models for production commercialisation WPs			
TO5.1	Creation of databases for ecodesign, criticality and circularity of new WBG materials and hybrid T-type power converters for LCA and circularity assessment.	WP1	
TO5.2	Development of LCA and circularity assessment of new materials, systems, processes and circular Business Models.	WP5	
TO5.3	Development of effective Circular Business Models for the new materials, components and powertrain systems.	WP6	
KPIs: 25% extension of life; 30% improvement in environmental and circular performance			
TO6: Promote collaborative research and interaction between academia and industry throughout the entire supply chain WPs			
TO6.1	Interaction with other EU initiatives: Industrial Battery Value Chain (Batteries), Cooperative Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM), Clean Hydrogen Europe (CHE) and Mission on Climate Neutral and Smart Cities.	WP6	
TO6.2	Interaction with other Research Initiatives: Creation of clustering and stakeholder platforms	WP6	
TO6.3	Effective communication and dissemination of results with the support of a recognized Advisory Board	WP6	
KPIs: 8 networking events			

RHODAS KoM 19-20 May 2022

7

Key Impacts Pathways (KPIs)		RHODAS	
KPI1: Demonstrate a minimum of 20% cost reduction of power electronic modules and inverters for a given power, to increase the overall affordability of EVs in mass production (in comparison to the cost of the best current-generation or close to market components at proposal submission time)			
RHODAS will develop novel converter topologies, integrating advanced WBG semiconductors for high-voltage (1000-1200V) traction power trains, demonstrating more efficient, cost-effective and power dense electronic modules (150-200 kW per axle). The integration of optimised thermal management systems within the Integrated Motor Drives (IMD) with advanced control strategies based on AI will contribute to achieve a 20% cost reduction of powertrains (Economic Outcomes&Impacts). Addressed in TO1 and TO3.			
KPI2: Significant advancements in efficiency (reduction of losses by 25%) and thermal performance (increased maximum operational temperature), both parameters versus the state of the art of the targeted application. This allows further driving range extension, faster charging and easier thermal management of the whole powertrain, as well as possible improvement in cabin-heating and defrosting in winter)			
RHODAS will develop novel control approaches improving the reliability while reducing the losses by 40%, apart from reducing noise and interferences, based on adaptive switching frequency control depending on the driving mode. The capabilities of the hybrid SiC-GaN converter allow new adaptive switching frequency strategies, and increase the temperature of operation up to 175°C. In addition, RHODAS will implement a more effective hybrid thermal management system combining micro liquid-cooling and air-cooling systems to mitigate negative effects of high current on health and ageing of the materials and components. This will significantly improve the thermal performance of the powertrains, which allows to extend the truck driving range in a 10% (Technological Outcomes&Impacts). Addressed in TO1.			

RHODAS KoM 19-20 May 2022

8

Key Impacts Pathways (KPIs)		RHODAS	
KPI3: Development of power electronics enabling drastic size and weight reductions for the electric drive, with significant advances beyond 3 kWh/kg or 20W/litre for a BEV)			
RHODAS will achieve more than 50% reduction of size and a 30% reduction of weight, taking advantage of the application of GaN and hybrid configurations of SiC-GaN to boost performance using the minimum amount of material. Significant power converter's volumetric and gravimetric power densities of 100kW/l and 50kW/kg are expected, which together with the integration of the motor within the IMD will help to achieve the ambitious targets for 2025 of 33kW/l and 5 kW/kg. At system-level, it means a reduction of the size, weight and cost of the power conditioning and thermal systems, resulting in a system volume reduction up to 40% (Technological Outcomes&Impacts). Addressed in TO2.			
KPI4: Facilitating the integration of power electronics in batteries/fuel cells and electric motor/axles (including modular approaches)			
RHODAS will adopt a modular and eco-design approach to unify 3D design and manufacture, performance and safety requirements, in order to create cost-efficient integrated IMD approaches. RHODAS will also implement the integration of the DC/DC into the DC/AC converters with a phase-based modular strategy, achieving a greater efficiency (+5%) in the IMD due to less energetic losses at the power conversion (~40%), and easier installation compared to present technologies. RHODAS circular design strategies will allow to develop circular product concepts, it will develop and fabricate highly integrated base modules for modular power electronics using 3D design and simulation for making easier further dismantling and reusing of components and materials. (Technological Outcomes&Impacts). Addressed in TO2 and TO5.			

RHODAS KoM 19-20 May 2022

9

Key Impacts Pathways (KPIs)		RHODAS	
KPI5: Increased reliability and availability of powertrain by intelligent control and diagnostics techniques, predictive maintenance of machine and inverter)			
RHODAS will implement the most advanced digital and simulation tools and AI technologies tools to improve the robustness, reliability and lifetime of power converters. First, RHODAS will achieve the effective integration of embedded sensors within the materials and components of the IMD for an advanced monitoring of the system in real time. Second, cloud-based intelligent control, simulation and diagnostics techniques will be implemented to improve the powertrain design, performance and lifetime using cloud computing, big data, AI, ML algorithms and IoT platforms. Digital Twin to further implement health management strategies for optimising design, operation, reduce failures and extend lifecycle of the materials, components and systems in a holistic approach. Ultimately, by applying its intelligent control and predictive maintenance technologies, RHODAS will achieve a 30% reduction of critical failures, 20% reduction of costs, 25% extension of lifetime and 30% improvement in LCA. (Technological Outcomes&Impacts). Addressed in TO3 and TO5.			
KPI6: Achieve automotive quality levels in the whole system with new, robust and reliable functionalities and materials)			
The use of new materials, TMS and converter designs in RHODAS will contribute to achieve more robust and reliable powertrain systems. In addition, the intelligent control and diagnostic techniques coupled with the predictive maintenance models will greatly contribute to achieve high quality levels. The quality of the powertrains using RHODAS technologies will be thoroughly evaluated by implementing performance and safety tests under different scenarios according to Automotive standards. (Scientific/Technological Outcomes&Impacts). Addressed in TO1, TO2, TO4 and TO5.			

RHODAS KoM 19-20 May 2022

10

Destination – Clean and competitive solutions for all transport modes - Expected Impacts		RHODAS	
KIP7: Towards climate-neutral and environmentally friendly mobility through clean solutions across all transport modes while increasing global competitiveness of the EU transport sector, notably through: - Transforming road transport to zero-emission mobility through all world-class European research and innovation and industrial system, ensuring that Europe remains world leader in innovation, production and services in relation to road transport (more detailed information below)			
RHODAS priority will be given to the development of drivetrains for zero emission heavy-duty long-haul vehicles, where progress is significantly lagging behind other sectors of road transportation in the EU by establishing a close collaboration between academia and industry to promote electric road transport, converting European mobility in a zero-emission one			
KIP8: Accelerated uptake of zero tailpipe emission, affordable, user-centric solutions (technologies and services) for road-based mobility all across Europe			
RHODAS technological innovation allows the possibility to apply the developed modular converter to not only heavy-duty vehicles, but also to all the other categories of electric vehicles such as Light-duty Vehicles (e.g. Passenger Cars), Medium-duty Passenger Vehicles, Light-Duty Trucks, either powered by batteries or fuel cells. This will allow to accelerate the market uptake of RHODAS innovations.			
KIP9: Increased user acceptance, improved air quality, a more circular economy and reduction of environmental impacts			
RHODAS represents a step forward to the reduction of transport environmental impacts, and promotes of a more sustainable circular economy, by supporting the growing demand from consumers for more environmentally friendly technologies and products			
KIP10: Effective design, assessment and deployment of innovative concepts in road vehicles and mobility			
RHODAS proposes a highly effective WBG-based power converter design for IMDs integrated with digital tools in a holistic approach. The use of Digital Twins promotes a strong collaboration between application producers designers and recyclers, increasing knowledge of material design for a better subsequent reuse and recycling. Measures such as better eco-design and waste prevention and reuse can bring net savings EU-wide to businesses while reducing total annual greenhouse gas emissions.			

RHODAS KoM 19-20 May 2022

11

RHODAS in summary		RHODAS	
- New powertrain generations, voltage levels, 400V, 800V and higher. -> 900-1000 VDC			
- System-partitioning/-integration: Intelligent, redundant and fail-safe topology/system architecture -> Fault Tolerance switches/legs redundancies / Three level conf./ DSS			
- Highly integrated power electronics: integrated on-board charger and traction inverter, integrated inverter and electric motor, integrated DC/DC and inverter, high-frequency DC/DC power conversion with WBG components -> hybrid SiC/GaN DC/DC + DC/AC + Motor			
- Topologies adapted to advanced WBG semiconductors -> Hybrid HF T-Type inverter + DC/DC			
- Control strategies with self-learning and intelligent monitoring capabilities, very high-frequency operation -> Intelligent switching according torque¤t, power and speed /digital twin			
- Joining and connecting technologies: low impedance connection and robustness against temperature; advanced interfaces for modular building blocks -> 3D optimized design			
- Thermal management: integrating cooling in housings, assemblies and component groups; direct liquid-cooling for high power, immersed power module, microchannel heatinks or heat pipes; air-cooling up to medium power levels -> microchannel heatinks&heat pipes.			
- Gate Drivers: integration of the driver component with the power module to limit the stray inductance between the gate driver and the semiconductor -> Integrated sensors, AGD with ringing (EMI) losses trade - off			

RHODAS KoM 19-20 May 2022

12

During the second day, WP7 was presented by UPC (Luis Romeral). In addition, the most relevant administrative and financial issues were presented and explained by UPC (Belén Calejo).

After the coffee break, Valeo started the technical discussions in WP1, in order to get organized for the further development of the activities in collaboration with the rest of participants of WP1.

2.3 MEETING NOTES

Apart from the Project and WPs presentations, some specific discussions at the end of the meeting were about:

- Project Governance and technical/management teams and committees, and project information flows, which must ensure fluid communication and rigorous and structured decision making.
- Software platforms and communications tools to be used for the Consortium and Committees during the project. Four different tools were described, which are: teleconf/online meeting tools, software repository for the partners' use, software repository for the storage of the open data used/produced by the partners, and website of the RHODaS project.
- Meetings frequency and schedule, distinguishing between formal governance meetings (Executive Committee, Scientific and Technical Committees, GA, ...) and ongoing technical meetings between and within WPs, to ensure smooth execution and achievement of objectives of the project

The Coordinator will prepare and discuss with the partners specific proposals on these issues, and the final decisions will be incorporated into the deliverables D7.1 Kick-off meeting report (M1, Responsible: UPC) and D7.2 Project management manual (M3, Responsible: UPC).

2.4 PICTURES OF THE EVENT

Figure 1. Presentation of the agenda and introduction from the Coordination Team

Figure 2. Presentation of the agenda and introduction from the Coordination Team

Figure 3. Presentation of beneficiary entities participating in RHODAS

Figure 4. Presentation of beneficiary entities participating in RHODAS

Figure 5. Presentation of beneficiary entities participating in RHODAS

Figure 6. Presentations of WPs by WP leaders

Figure 7. Presentations of WPs by WP leaders

Figure 8. Technical and organisational discussion for WP1 (VALEO)

Figure 9. Technical and organisational discussion for WP1 (VALEO)

Figure 10. Participants attending the RHODAS kick off meeting

3. THE RHODaS PROJECT

3.1 CONCEPT

The main objective of the RHODaS project is to improve the efficiency of electric Integrated Motor Drive (IMD) powertrains for multiple wheel drive architectures (WBG-based power electronics; 1200/1700VDC; 150 kW per axle) for heavy-duty long-haul vehicles, while reducing their size and cost by using novel semiconductor materials, optimal thermal management strategies and disruptive topologies of power converters in a modular approach. Also improved resilience is achieved thanks to the application of intelligent control and diagnostics techniques, as well as (data-driven) predictive maintenance of the powertrain system and components. In addition, relevant environmental, social and economic issues are considered from the design, to facilitate scalability while ensuring sustainability, circularity and social acceptance.

3.2 PROJECT SCOPE

In the project RHODaS, cutting-edge technologies in the field of semiconductor materials, electronics, power converters and thermal management are combined with advanced modelling and simulation techniques and the effective application of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs). The developments in RHODaS go from materials to components and systems, following a three-stage methodology based in: 1) technology development and integration; 2) application of eco-design to ensure circularity of materials and processes; 3) validation of the solution in a relevant environment, which will be applied at the different levels (materials, components and systems). The results obtained in the validation phase at each level will be used as inputs in superior levels (from materials to systems) and for optimising previous development in an iterative approach, towards the final validation of a prototype integrating all the developments carried out throughout the project. In Figure 11, a simplified scheme of the RHODaS methodology and the project concept are represented, indicating the main partners that will lead the different areas of development.

Figure 11. General scheme of the technologies, designs and processes developed under the RHODaS action and main partners.

The RHODaS project aims at developing disruptive topologies of power converters using new semiconductor materials as well as cutting-edge digital technologies to improve architecture efficiency, power density, reliability, cost and sustainability. Moreover, multi-disciplinary approaches of modular power electronics for Integrated Motor Drive (IMD) and ecodesign considerations are addressed, to create compact solutions that can be integrated in a wide range and heavy-duty vehicles, enabling these electric vehicles to be more sustainable and autonomous throughout the entire lifecycle of their components. Nevertheless, power electronics solutions that use Wide Band Gap (WBG) devices can also be applied to light-duty vehicle types M and L, with competitive advantages on the efficiency and power densities compared with current technologies. Finally, the RHODaS project targets the validation of the proposed solutions in electric drivetrains of 1200V for zero emissions class N3 (carriage of goods > 12 tonnes) and O4 (trailers >10 Tonnes), which correspond to USA Class 7-8 heavy duty vehicles (>12 Tonnes) and beyond.

3.3 PROJECT OBJECTIVES

Table 1. List of RODHaS objectives and KPIs.

TO1. Improve efficiency and performance of power converters while increasing affordability of powertrains for heavy-duty EVs		WPs
TO1.1	Develop disruptive T-type multilevel converter topologies based on hybrid fault tolerant SiC-GaN DC/DC-DC/AC architectures for high-voltage ($\geq 1000V$, being the target 1200V) traction power trains, allowing more efficient and power dense power electronic converters (about 150 kW per axel, peak efficiency >98%), and reducing the complexity of the controls.	WP2
TO1.2	Develop new adaptive switching frequency control approaches to further improve the efficiency according to the driving mode, by taking advantage of the WBG wide frequency range ($50 \text{ kHz} < f < 100 \text{ kHz}$ for high power converters). Total power losses reduction >40% and EMI reduction is expected by adapting the devices' switching to the torque-speed operating point.	WP2
TO1.3	Develop novel power converter control strategies with self-learning and intelligent monitoring capabilities, suitable for very high-frequency operation, and fault detection and mitigation through Fault Tolerant Control.	WP2
TO1.4	Develop a more effective hybrid thermal management system (TMS) of the IMD combining liquid-cooling and air-cooling to mitigate negative effects of high current on health and ageing of the materials and components.	WP3
KPIs: 40% reduction of thermal losses, temperature operation up to 175°C, truck driving range +10%		
TO2. Reduce size and weight of the power converters		WPs
TO2.1	Effective application of WBG semiconductor materials in a hybrid configuration to boost performance using the minimum amount of material.	WP2
TO2.2	Develop and fabricate highly integrated base modules for modular power electronics using 3D design and simulation.	WP2 WP3
TO2.3	Achieve compact integration of gate drivers in high-frequency power modules with minimum interferences.	WP2
KPIs: 50% reduction of size, 30% reduction of weight, 15 dB reduction of EMI noise		
TO3. Effective application of digital technologies and sensors for advanced on-line monitoring and intelligent estimation and prediction of states based in advanced modelling and prediction techniques using Big Data Analysis and Artificial Intelligence		WPs
TO3.1	Design effective sensor networks able to detect changes in relevant parameters at material, component and system level to develop more accurate models for characterisation and control.	WP3

TO3.2	Provide an efficient service layer by creating a new software architecture in the cloud (IoT platform) including data acquisition, storage, processing and visualisation.	WP4
TO3.3	Develop and integrate advanced physic and data-driven models in a complete Digital Twin using data provided by the sensor networks. These models are updated in real-time by applying AI and ML techniques.	WP4
TO3.3	Integration of new smart functionalities, such as state estimation and prediction of materials components and systems.	WP4
TO3.4	Develop decision support systems for fault detection, identification and correction.	WP4
TO3.5	Implement AI based predictive maintenance functionalities and health management strategies for optimising operation, cost and lifecycle of the materials, components and systems, including power train fault tolerant control.	WP4
KPIs: 30% reduction of failures, 20% reduction of costs, 25% extension of lifetime		
TO4. Effective integration of the power electronics and TMS in a modular and compact IMD to evaluate the overall performance in a complete e-axel test bench		WPs
TO4.1	Validate the operation and performance of the new power converters in a complete system under a wide range of operating conditions, following Automotive quality and safety standards.	WP5
TO4.2	Create, optimise and update the holistic model of the complete powertrain, including materials, components and systems, to validate accuracy of the digital twin and its functionalities.	WP4 WP5
TO4.3	Validate the fault tolerance operation of the power converters on a complete e-axel testbench.	WP5
KPIs: Increase total IMD efficiency in more than 5%; Predict converter RUL with accuracy >75%; Reduction of converter losses by 75% over a driving cycle.		
TO5. Integration of ecodesign, material criticality and circularity considerations into the RHODaS powertrain solution, as well as viable circular business models for their future commercialisation		WPs
TO5.1	Creation of databases for ecodesign, criticality and circularity of new WBG materials and hybrid T-type power converters for LCA and circularity assessment.	WP1
TO5.2	Development of LCA and circularity assessment of new materials, systems, processes and circular Business Models.	WP5
TO5.3	Development of effective Circular Business Models for the new materials, components and powertrain systems.	WP6
KPIs: 25% extension of life, 30% improvement in environmental and circular performance		
TO6 Promote collaborative research and interaction between academia and industry throughout the entire supply chain		WPs
TO6.1	Interaction with other EU initiatives: Industrial Battery Value Chain (Batteries), Cooperative Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM), Clean Hydrogen Europe (CHE) and the Mission on Climate Neutral and Smart Cities.	WP6
TO6.2	Interaction with other Research Initiatives. Creation of clustering and stakeholder platforms	WP6
TO6.3	Effective communication and dissemination of results with the support of a recognised Advisory Board	WP6
KPIs: 8 networking events		

3.4 PROJECT IMPACT

3.4.1 TECHNOLOGICAL IMPACT

KIP1: Demonstrate a minimum of 20% cost reduction of power electronic modules and inverters for a given power, to increase the overall affordability of EVs in mass production (in comparison to the cost of the best current-generation or close to market components at proposal submission time).

Cost reduction and increased power density combined with longer lifetime are the main challenges for the development of a new generation of inverters. RHODaS will develop novel converter topologies, integrating advanced WBG semiconductors for high-voltage (1000-1200V-1700V) traction power trains, demonstrating more efficient, cost-effective and power dense electronic modules (150-200 kW per axle). In addition to the use of novel semiconductor materials and the integration of optimised thermal management systems within the Integrated Motor Drives (IMD) with advanced control strategies based on AI will contribute to achieve a 20% cost reduction of powertrains, increasing the affordability and promoting a full-market penetration of heavy-duty EVs

(Economic Outcomes&Impacts). Addressed in TO1 and TO3.

KIP2: Significant advancements in efficiency (reduction of losses by 25%) and thermal performance (increased maximum operational temperature), both parameters versus the state of the art of the targeted application. This allows further driving range extension, faster charging and easier thermal management of the whole powertrain, as well as possible improvement in cabin-heating and defrosting in winter.

Exploiting the wide frequency range of the WBG materials integrated in the powertrains, RHODaS will develop novel control approaches improving the reliability while reducing the losses by 40%, apart from reducing noise and interferences, based on adaptive switching frequency control depending on the driving mode. The capabilities hybrid SiC/GaN switches reduce the complexity of the control, allowing new adaptive switching frequency strategies, and increase the temperature of operation up to 175°C. In addition, RHODaS will implement a more effective hybrid thermal management system combining micro liquid- cooling and air-cooling systems to mitigate negative effects of high current on health and ageing of the materials and components. This will significantly improve the thermal performance of the powertrains, which allows to extend the truck driving range in a 10%

(Technological Outcomes&Impacts). Addressed in TO1.

KIP3: Development of power electronics enabling drastic size and weight reductions for the electric drive, with significant advances beyond 5 kW/kg or 20kW/litre for a BEV.

One of the biggest challenges of power electronics in electric vehicles is increasing the power density, developing smaller components, handling more power while fitting in smaller packages: in other words, to achieve a significant reduction in terms of both size and weight. RHODaS will achieve more than 50% reduction of size and a 30% reduction of weight, taking advantage of the application of GaN and hybrid configurations of SiC-GaN to boost performance using the minimum amount of material, according to ecodesign principles. Significant power converter's volumetric and gravimetric power densities of 100kW/l and 50kW/kg are expected, which together with the integration of the motor within the IMD will help to achieve the ambitious targets for 2025 of 33kW/l and 5 kW/kg. At system-level, the benefits of using the new semiconductors materials

include the possibility of further reducing the size, weight and cost of the power conditioning and thermal systems, resulting in a system volume reduction up to 40%

(Technological Outcomes&Impacts). Addressed in TO2.

KIP4: Facilitating the integration of power electronics in batteries/fuel cells and electric motors/axles (including modular approaches).

RHODaS will adopt a modular and eco-design approach to unify 3D design and manufacture, performance and safety requirements, in order to create cost-efficient integrated IMD approaches. RHODaS will also implement the integration of the DC/DC into the DC/AC converters with a phase-based modular strategy, achieving a greater efficiency level (+5%) in the IMD due to less energetic losses at the power conversion (-40%), and easier installation compared to present technologies. RHODaS circular design strategies will allow to develop circular product concepts: it will develop and fabricate highly integrated base modules for modular power electronics using 3D design and simulation for making easier further dismantling and reusing of components and materials.

(Technological Outcomes&Impacts). Addressed in TO2 and TO5.

KIP5: Increased reliability and availability of powertrain by intelligent control and diagnostics techniques, predictive maintenance of machine and inverter.

RHODaS will implement the most advanced digital and simulation tools and AI technologies tools to improve the robustness, reliability and lifetime of power converters. First, RHODaS will achieve the effective integration of embedded sensors within the materials and components of the IMD for an advanced monitoring of the system in real time. Second, cloud-based intelligent control, simulation and diagnostics techniques will be implemented to improve the powertrain design, performance and lifetime using cloud computing, big data, AI, ML algorithms and IoT platforms. This will allow to detect changes in relevant operation parameters at material, component and system level in real time to develop physic and data-driven models which are integrated in a complete Digital Twin to further implement health management strategies for optimising design, operation, reduce failures and extend lifecycle of the materials. components and systems in a holistic approach. Ultimately, by applying its intelligent control and predictive maintenance technologies, RHODaS will achieve a 30% reduction of critical failures, 20% reduction of costs, 25% extension of lifetime and 30% improvement in LCA.

(Technological Outcomes&Impacts). Addressed in TO3 and TO5.

KIP6: Achieve automotive quality levels in the whole system with new, robust and reliable functionalities and materials.

The use of new materials, TMS and converter designs in RHODaS will contribute to achieve more robust and reliable powertrain systems. In addition, the intelligent control and diagnostic techniques coupled with the predictive maintenance models will greatly contribute to achieve high quality levels. The quality of the powertrains using RHODaS technologies will be thoroughly evaluated by implementing performance and safety tests under different scenarios according to Automotive standards.

(Scientific/Technological Outcomes&Impacts). Addressed in TO1, TO2, TO4 and TO5.

3.4.2 ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT

KIP7: “Towards climate-neutral and environmentally friendly mobility through clean solutions across all transport modes while increasing global competitiveness of the EU transport sector”, notably through: Transforming road transport to zero-emission mobility through a world-class European research and innovation and industrial system, ensuring that Europe remains world leader in innovation, production and services in relation to road transport (more detailed information below).

Introduction of stringent emission regulation policies by the European Union, aiming at improving the climate and environmental footprint of the transport sector, is contributing towards the adoption of technologically advanced low-emission heavy-duty trucks. In December 2018, Council of European Union agreed on a legislative proposal to mandate CO₂ emission standards for heavy-duty trucks in European countries. According to this proposal, in 2025, the emission level reduced by 15% compared to 2019, with a further reduction of around 30% by 2030 and 100% by 2050. In line with these objectives, in RHODaS, priority will be given to the development of drivetrains for zero emission heavy-duty long-haul vehicles, where progress is significantly lagging behind other sectors of road transportation in the EU by establishing a close collaboration between academia and industry to promote electric road transport, converting European mobility in a zero-emission one –with significant positive effects on the air quality- and boosting the global competitiveness of the EU transport sector.

(Scientific/Societal Outcomes&Impacts). Addressed in TO4, TO5 and TO6.

KIP8: Accelerated uptake of zero tailpipe emission, affordable, user-centric solutions (technologies and services) for road-based mobility all across Europe.

The key aspect of RHODaS technological innovation is the possibility to apply the developed modular converter to not only heavy-duty vehicles, but also to all the other categories of electric vehicles such as Light-duty Vehicles (e.g., Passenger Cars), Medium-duty Passenger Vehicles, Light-Duty Trucks, either powered by batteries or fuel cells. This feature alone will allow to accelerate the market uptake of RHODaS innovations. In addition, the reduction of cost, the increase of power densities, efficiency, robustness, reliability and affordability of the powertrain will be crucial in speeding up the market uptake. Finally, the participation of VAL and VS, as well as the close collaboration with the RHODaS Advisory Board will boost the uptake of the project innovations in their manufacturing and production chain. In addition, relevant environmental, social and economic issues are considered from the design (LCA, LCC and Eco-design), to facilitate scalability while ensuring the development of affordable and reliable user-centric solution, whose main pillars are the sustainability, recyclability and circularity.

(Economic/Technological Outcomes&Impacts). Addressed in TO4, TO5 and TO6.

KIP9: Increased user acceptance, improved air quality, a more circular economy and reduction of environmental impacts.

By including environmentally friendly and ecodesign approaches, RHODaS aims at promoting an increase in the societal awareness and user acceptance of the benefits of the innovative electric powertrain developed and, more in general, of electric heavy-duty

¹https://www.graphicalresearch.com/industry-insights/1468/europe-heavy-duty-trucks-market?gclid=Cj0KCQjwxdSHBhCdARIsAG6zh1VHrkqHuIEOcaMy8ZqpiBTeyC9XnD4N6_5Tj5BUYo42WOhShad4NtsaAk9REALw_wcB

vehicles utilisation: through the actions that will be implemented, the project will constantly pursue engaging society to ensure wider public acceptance by providing an increased understanding of the benefits EVs utilisation for an improved air quality in Europe. Consumers' expectations regarding EVs environmental benefits will be met, while at the same time, being able to benefit from improved formulations from the technological point of view. In conclusion, RHODaS represents a step forward to the reduction of transport environmental impacts, and promotes of a more sustainable circular economy, by supporting the growing demand from consumers for more environmentally friendly technologies and products.

(Societal Outcomes&Impacts) Addressed in TO4 and TO6.

KIP10: Effective design, assessment and deployment of innovative concepts in road vehicles and mobility

In RHODaS, a highly effective WGB-based power converter design for IMDs is integrated with digital tools in a holistic approach, where ecodesign and circularity concepts are addressed, to create compact and modular solutions that can be integrated in a wide range of heavy-duty vehicles –but also easily applicable to light-duty vehicles– enabling these electric vehicles to be more sustainable and autonomous throughout the entire lifecycle of their components. The compact and optimised design of the IMD will reduce cables, connections and losses between power electronics and motor windings, and eliminates voltage overshoots inherent to high switching frequency of WBG devices, as well as produced EMI. The use of Digital Twins promotes a strong collaboration between application producers/designers and recyclers, increasing knowledge of material design for a better subsequent reuse and recycling. A specific eco-design model will be developed at the beginning of the project to remove the knowledge gap between technical performances of the selected materials and their ability to be recycled, which will be also integrated in the Digital Twin to optimise designs and processes (Scientific Outcomes&Impacts). Measures such as better eco-design and waste prevention and reuse can bring net savings EU-wide to businesses while reducing total annual greenhouse gas emissions. Thus, RHODaS will assess circular business models considering materials and components, which can be applied in other sectors, contributing to reducing environmental impacts to foster the commercial deployment of these technologies.

(Societal Outcomes&Impacts). Addressed in TO3, TO4 and TO6.

4. RHODaS WORK PLAN

An overview of the RHODaS work plan, project milestones, Gantt chart and flow of work is provided in this section

4.1 PROJECT WORK PLANS

The schedule for project Work Plans, together with the partner responsible for supervision is listed in Figure 12. The RHODaS project is composed of 7 work packages to develop, validate and assess the new technologies proposed, in order to achieve the strategic objectives of the project in 42 months. In the following Table 2, the list of Work Packages (WP), WP leaders and the efforts and duration of each WP are presented, as well as deliverables and milestones list in Table 3 and Table 4, respectively.

Figure 12. RHODaS Work flow

Table 2. List of Work Packages

WP#	Work Package Title	Lead	Short Name	PM	Start	End
WP1	System specs; components and materials. Ecodesign considerations	VALEO	VAL	76	01/05/22 (M1)	31/07/23 (M15)
WP2	Design of electric and electronic components	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya	UPC	117	01/10/22 (M6)	31/07/24 (M27)
WP3	Thermal Management System	Aarhus University	AU	76	01/01/23 (M9)	31/08/24 (M28)
WP4	Software design and development	NVISION	NION	59	01/02/23 (M10)	01/01/25 (M35)
WP5	Integration, testing and technical and environmental validation	BOSMAL	BOS	171	01/12/23 (M20)	31/10/25 (M42)
WP6	Exploitation, Commm & Diss	KNEIA	KNEIA	84	01/05/22 (M1)	31/10/25 (M42)

WP7	Project management and Coordination	Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya	UPC	50	01/05/22 (M1)	31/10/25 (M42)
-----	-------------------------------------	--------------------------------------	-----	----	------------------	-------------------

TOTAL PM: 633

Table 3. List of Deliverables

Nº	Deliverable Name	WP	Partner	Type	Dis. level	Due date
D1.1	System specifications and requirements for electric and electronic system including thermal management system	1	UPC	R	PU	M6, M9
D1.2	Materials specifications and requirements for active and passive electronic components. Selection matrix and integration strategies.	1	AIT	R	PU	M10, M15
D1.3	Ecodesign guideline covering environmental, material criticality and circularity considerations	1	TUW	R	PU	M9, M15
D1.4	Hardware and software specifications of the prototypes for validation	1	VAL	R	CO	M12
D1.5	Metrics and use cases	1	VAL	R	CO	M15
D2.1	Intelligent power modules with integrated sensors and OTP/OCP circuits	2	UPC	R	PU	M16
D2.2	Active gate drivers for high-power, high-frequency WBG devices	2	UPC	R	PU	M20
D2.3	Power converter design, modelling and simulation	2	AIT	R	CO	M24
D2.4	Experimental results and validation of lab-scale power converters prototypes	2	BOS	R	PU	M27
D3.1	Thermal Management System strategies, modelling and simulations	3	AU	R	PU	M20
D3.2	3D modelling of the DC/DC and DC/AC converters	3	AIT	R	CO	M24
D3.3	Lab testing and validation of the Thermal Management System	3	BOS	R	PU	M28
D4.1	Fault tolerant control of SiC/GaN power converters	4	UPC	R	PU	M21, M29
D4.2	Decision Support Systems to improve IMD control, performance and health	4	NION	R	CO	M31
D4.3	Definition and implementation of a holistic digital twin of the IMD	4	AU	R	PU	M32
D4.4	Cloud-based service layer: RHODaS IoT platform	4	NION	OTHER	CO	M25, M33
D4.5	Integration of the software modules and validation of the digital tools	4	NION	R	CO	M35
D5.1	Description of the final prototype of the RHODaS hybrid T-Type power converter. Definition of scenarios and procedures for validation	5	AIT	R	PU	M34
D5.2	Final prototype of the RHODaS hybrid T-Type power converter	5	UPC	DEM	CO	M34
D5.3	Analysis of results of the switching tests of the converters	5	AIT	R	PU	M36

D5.4	Results of the integration and characterisation of the IMD system in a complete e-axel	5	VAL	R	CO	M42
D5.5	Environmental, criticality and circularity assessment of materials, systems and components	5	TUW	R	PU	M42
D5.6	Standardisation of the IMD system and component	5	BOS	R	CO	M42
D6.1	Project website	6	KNEIA	DEC	PU	M6
D6.2	Project videos	6	KNEIA	DEC	PU	M24, M42
D6.3	Plan of Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication	6	KNEIA	R	PU	M6, M24, M42
D6.4	Circular Business Models	6	VAL	R	CO	M24, M42
D6.5	Multistakeholder Platform	6	KNEIA	R	PU	M30
D6.6	Research Ownership List	6	VAL	R	CO	M42
D7.1	Kick-Off Meeting report	7	UPC	R	PU	M1
D7.2	Project Management Handbook.	7	UPC	R	CO	M3
D7.3	Data Management Plan	7	UPC	DMP	CO	M6, M42
D7.4	Risk Management Plan	7	UPC	R	CO	M6, M24, M42
D7.5	Gender Action Plan and Ethics considerations	7	UPC	ETHICS	PU	M6

Table 4. List of Milestones

Nº	Milestone name	Related WP	Due date	Means of verification
MS1	Specifications of materials, components and systems are set	WP1	M11	D1.4
MS2	Metrics and use cases for validation tests are specified	WP1	M15	D1,5
MS3	Validation of the operation of the Smart Power Modules SiC/GaN controlled by active gate drivers is completed according to KPIs	WP2	M20	D2.1; D2.2
MS4	Experimental validation of the power converters and ancillary circuits is completed according to KPIs	WP2	M27	D2.4
MS5	The simulation toolbox for thermal modelling is developed and validated	WP3	M20	D3.1
MS6	Optimal 3D design of the high-power converter 150kW/1200VDC is completed	WP3	M24	D3.2
MS7	DSS and DT are developed and ready for integration	WP4	M32	D4.2, D4.3
MS8	Successful integration of SW modules, GUIs, communications and APIs in the IoT is validated	WP4	M35	D 4.5
MS9	Characterisation of e-axel performance is complete	WP5	M40	D5.3, D5.4
MS10	Improvements of 30% in LCA are demonstrated	WP5	M42	D5.5
MS11	Project action successfully implemented and finalised	WP7	M42	Final report

4.3 RISK REGISTER

The Project Coordinator (COO) will be in charge of the risk management, and together with the Work Package Leaders (WPLs), will continuously monitor and identify potential areas of risk developing in the project. In close collaboration with the Exploitation Manager (EM), the COO will specifically manage exploitation, market and business-related risks, whereas the Scientific and Technical Manager will provide support by looking at technical-related risks. The Communication and Dissemination and Exploitation Managers will pay special attention to exploitation, Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and communication, while the PC will be in charge of the management-related risks.

For any risk identified, a resolution plan will be proposed either by the Task Leader with the support of the COO. The work plan will be appropriately adapted for minor technical or organisational changes. Risks which require major changes in the overall work plan will be discussed by the Executive Board. In order to counter risk occurrences during the entire project life cycle, there is a need to perform Risk Response Control that includes the execution of the risk management plan, which will be regularly updated (at each consortium meeting that will be held every six months).

The project at the outset has a variety of identified risks of a technical, economic and social nature as outlined in Table 5.

Table 5. Risk Register

Description of risk, severity and likelihood	WP	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Fail in defining the preliminary specifications of the system (S: high; I: medium)	WP1	An iterative methodology for the development of the different components in WPs 1-4 is followed to maximise the performance of the overall solution. Preliminary specifications are thus revised and optimised throughout the project until the final integration and validation
Initially selected converter type and configuration turns out to be not suitable (S: high; L: low)	WP2	Early evaluation of possibilities and replacement by another better suited type or configuration (three level NPC converter, two-level converter, etc)
Not possible to meet the defined KPIs regarding increased power density (S: high; L: high)	WP2	Start a detailed density estimation as early as possible in the project and follow up regularly during the project to highlight critical deviation from the estimations already in the design phase where mitigation can be possible (for instance, allowing higher average Tj temperatures)
Switching control strategies are not deployed on time (S: medium; L: medium)	WP2	Overlap and follow-up of tasks in WP2, WP3 and WP4
Mismatch in between the numerical thermo-electric models and experimental results (S: medium; L: low)	WP3	Additional laboratory measures and data collection to launch optimal digital models fitting through AI techniques.
Temperature increments are greater than desired (S: medium; L: low)	WP3	AU have expertise on thermal management and heat transfer enhancement for power electronics. A redesign of the TMS and heatsinks will be made and new materials will be selected and experimentally validated before applied to the prototypes.

Space and weight requirement related to TMS become hard to meet (S: high; L: medium)	WP3	Multiple solutions are considered for design optimisation and heat transfer enhancement. New materials with lower Rth will be selected and used, despite their higher costs.
Multiple model integration and synchronisation fails (S: medium; L: medium)	WP4	A review of protocols for software development defined early in the project will be made, and will be ensured that all partners involved in programming and communication follows the same structure and standards.
Incompatible integration of software modules (S: medium; L: low)	WP4	Several compatibility tests are performed before final integration. Different communication protocols are selected to ensure viable alternatives in advance.
Limited access to testing/characterisation facilities (S: medium; L: medium)	WP2- WP5	Several testing/characterisation infrastructures are available within the RHODaS consortium, so temporary replacement by testing infrastructure of another partner is possible
Components selected for prototype development are late (S: medium; L: low)	WP2- WP4	Prompt selection of the required components for ensuring the project schedule. Continuous follow-up on such selection will be done.
Laboratory availability due to COVID restrictions (S: medium; L: low)	WP2- WP5	The partners will have the test schedule early in the project lifespan to ensure availability. Common project calendars will be shared with such aim.
Incompatibilities of individual components avoids proper integration of power converters, IMD or e-axel systems (S: medium; L: low)	WP5	The system specifications, especially communications and connections, are carefully defined in WP1 at material, component and system level and are modified, if necessary, according to the results of the integration and validation in WP5, following an iterative process of lean development to ensure the best performance
Not possible to test the prototype, because one the subsystems is not ready (S: high; L: high)	WP5	In order to deliver a high-quality demonstrator, all subsystems are designed and developed under a contingency plan for avoiding delays. In this way, the plan B demonstrator will always be operational, to ensure that the overall test with all the subsystems can be done.
Lack of appropriate data in the LCA databases related to the circular economy of WBG materials (S: medium; L: medium)	WP5	Within RHODaS, close collaboration with different manufacturers is established through the IAB, which are committed to provide materials, as well as sufficient initial data for LCA analyses. Additional data will be sourced from partners or existing networks as needed.
Lack of understanding of global scenarios and market or technological trends (S: high; L: low)	WP6	All the partners have a pluri-annual overall vision of technology trends in the sector. Specific actions will be considered to involve experts from industry to notify any strategic orientation, as well as other experts from the consortium network. The IAB goal will be to ensure strategic directions.
The regulatory environment remains unattractive for the EV sector (S: high; L: low)	WP6	Active communications with key stakeholders, for example, through the IAB and the direct industry contacts within the different networks in which the partners are involved

During the exploitation plan, problems with Intellectual Property arise among partners (S: medium; L: low)	WP6	As a means of enforcing an intellectual property policy, all partners in the project will develop best practice and adopt a participation agreement, which confirms acceptance of the policy by employees, researchers and will clearly define protocols and procedures by which any intellectual property arising will be exploited. All partners will sign-up and confirm the IP management as part of an overarching CA. The PC will solve any IPR-related issue that could not be tackled internally or by merely following the CA or the GA.
Quantifying the impact of the project to EU consumers, business, government & society (S: medium; L: low)	WP6	The consortium has engaged partners with strong knowledge of the sector and experts in business plan and market analysis. This will ensure the successful results of RHODaS are leveraged to identify routes for innovation, diffusion and socio-economic impact on society, Academia, SMEs and Industry.
Poor cooperation between the partners (S: high; L: low)	WP7	Track record for previous co-operation between the research partners, complementary roles of the partners, mobility of researchers, efficient and experienced project management, meetings, etc.
Lack of consensus within the consortium over strategy, technical work and other project Mgmt. concerns (S: high; L: low)	WP7	Procedures for facilitating effective decision making will be employed as outlined in the implementation plan, the project coordinator will look at conflict resolution as required by the situation.
A partner wishes to leave the Consortium (S: high; L: low)	WP7	Implement sanctions in the Consortium Agreement, divide task of the leaving party within the consortium if applicable or contract a new partner with the required expertise
Key person(s) leaves the project (S: low; L: medium)	WP7	Share the knowledge with sufficient number of employees and partners. Provide full documentation of the work performed during the project.
Underestimate the time needed to perform a given task (S: high; L: low)	WP7	Risk mitigation measure: monitor performance and deliverables against time schedule of each task & use frequent planning, engagement, control and review. In case of being late, reinforce the team, hire more people or reallocate PMs between tasks if possible. If necessary, postpone other less critical tasks to concentrate the force into the critical tasks being late.
Delays in the deliverables (S: high; L: medium)	WP7	Build buffers in the critical paths to ensure deadlines are met

5. MANAGEMENT STRUCTURE

To ensure smooth operation of project progress, a system of management structure has been implemented in the RHODaS, which will be presented in next sections.

5.1 PROJECT GOVERNANCE

The consortium-agreed governance structure has been conceived in order to provide an adequate level of control and the ability to steer the various parties and their roles. The main elements of the management structure and activities, including the WP management overview, are summarized in Figure 13.

Figure 13. RHODaS Management structure

5.1.1 THE PROJECT COORDINATION TEAM

The Coordinator (UPC), jointly with the Project Coordination Team (PCT), will ensure that all partners are fully informed of the status of the project and upcoming work, handles administrative tasks for the project management, and ensures the quality of the action by implementing quality procedures for the project. Also, gather, monitor and consolidate scientific and technical content for periodical reports, consolidate the project's deliverables and reports, and maintain its quality assurance including submission to the EC

Specifically, **the Coordinator (COO) is expected to:**

- Act as the intermediary for all communications between the beneficiaries and the EC;
- Monitor and control the project's work plan and ensure the action is implemented properly;
- Prepare, manage and coordinate the project's financial checks;
- Administer project resources including budget-related issues;
- Handle financial management including distribution of payments to the beneficiaries;
- Facilitate communication within the consortium on administrative matters;
- Handle outstanding administrative issues like contract amendments;
- Oversee the provision of a project management electronic platform;

Starting with a project kick-off meeting (M1), the Project Coordinator (COO) and the PCT will lead by-monthly meetings with the Project Executive Board (PEB), regular work package meetings, and at least one General Assembly meeting (GA) per year, where he will coordinate an in-depth discussion of the necessary actions and collaborations between partners and WPs.

This comprises a variety of tasks not linked to any specific deliverable, including the preparation of meeting agendas, advice and support to partners on technical issues, monitoring gender equality, correspondence with external organizations (e.g. answering queries about the project) and close collaboration within the management team, including the rest of the Coordination Team members, the Technical & Scientific Committee and the Exploitation, Communications and Dissemination managers (KNEIA and VALEO), to ensure the smooth running of the project and the diffusion and exploitation of the results.

Particular attention will be paid to the risks identified in Table 5, which can affect the developments. Risk management will be the responsibility of the Project Coordination Team (PCT), composed by the Coordinator (Luis Romeral) and the Project Management Assistant partner NION (José Saez), which will be continually informed about the progress of work (through internal reports, meetings etc.) in order to be able to early identify any potential problems. Solutions will be discussed at a task level, WP level, or with the Executive Board, composed by all WP Leaders. Particular attention will be paid to risks regarding data collection and management. Mitigation plans for technical issues are outlined in Table 5.

Problems and contingency plans will be constantly reviewed by the relevant partners and WP leaders and, if required, revised by the PCT and the EB, in preparation of GA and Project Reporting meetings. The PCT ensures the agreed management procedures in order to solve internal problems, which could arise in such a large and diverse consortium of partners. The Coordinator will keep the EU Project Officer informed of the project status and of any problems, delays, or proposed adjustments.

5.1.2 THE PROJECT EXECUTIVE BOARD

The highest level of management in the project will be exercised by the Project Executive Board (PEB), which forms the supervisory body for the execution of the Project and will have overall responsibility for addressing the project technical, financial, administrative and collaborative aspects. The PEB will be composed by key representatives of each

partner of the Consortium, with the power of engaging the company in any decision, and will normally meet bi-monthly as minimum. The PEB will make decisions by majority voting, with a casting vote by the COO if required. The PEB will, in particular:

- Define the political and strategic orientation for conducting the project according to the terms of the contract;
- Monitor the progress of the project: review the technical progress and decide appropriate amendments to the work plan according to the recommendations of the Project Coordination Team (PCT), as well as review the consortium budget and financial allocation between partners according to the project progress; Decide upon the necessity to request contract modifications to the European Commission, and prepare requests for amendments;
- Preparation of meetings & proposing decisions;
- Assess the impact of any strategic changes to the contract suggested by the European Commission and respond accordingly;
- Preserve compliance with Consortium Plan & project;
- Maintaining consensual relations between partners;
- Decide upon the motivated exclusion of a partner, or the inclusion of a new partner;
- Resolve any conflict, technical, managerial or financial that may appear amongst the project partners;
- Review Data & Deliverables;
- Review the policy and strategy for dissemination and publicity of the project;
- Review the policy in terms of Intellectual Property Rights, foreground knowledge generated during the project and sharing;
- Oversee and review the Project Coordinator (COO) management.

5.1.3 THE SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL COMMITTEE

The Scientific and Technical Committee (STC) will be responsible for the technical progress of the project, and for the impulse and promotion of the scientific dissemination of the results of the project (preferably in Open Source publications), with the support of the leaders of each technical work package. Specifically, the STC will have significant role and together the PCT will be responsible for the coordination of the technical aspects of the project and the proper identification of all interfaces. To achieve these objectives, the STC will organize technical meetings every 3 months through a virtual platform with the participation of the Work-Package leaders and the PCT.

The main tasks of the STC are:

- Responsible for technical and scientific progress of the project and for completing successfully the S&T objectives and activities of the project in a timely manner.
- Responsible for the adequate focus and co-ordination of technical work within the consortium.
- Provide links of the project with other efforts, projects and overall initiatives that are related to the theme of the project either from within the enterprises or outside of the enterprises at a national or international level.

- When necessary, e.g. due to a technological breakthrough, adjusts the content and direction of research.
- Identify possible technical problems and conflicts between the WPs that may restrain the projects technical evolution and will convoke a meeting for their resolution.
- The STC is expected to meet in average 4 times a year. Telephone and web meetings will be used complementary to the physical meetings for keeping close track to the development of the subprojects.

At the STC Meetings, the WP Leaders will report the work status following the decision taking procedure established. The STC can request an urgent PEB meeting to the COO in case a strategic decision related to a scientific or technical matter has to be made.

5.1.4 PROJECT COORDINATION AND ADMINISTRATIVE MGMT

Project administration and management will be undertaken by the Project Coordinator (and WP7 leader), UPC, and the Project Coordination Team, and will involve:

- Obtaining audit certificates from the contractors and financial security details when requested;
- Coordination of the overall contractual, financial and administrative aspects, including the reporting of the project's financial and budgetary status to the PEB and the European Commission;
- Collection and submission of the cost statements for the project to the European Commission;
- Coordinating communication between the project and the European Commission;
- Organising meetings of the PEB as and when required;
- Performing inter-work-package coordination by providing advice to the Work-package Leaders;
- Organising and maintaining a central repository for deliverables, to store and organise intermediate results and the finals deliverables, and participating in deliverable reviews;
- Organising project reviews by the EC and ensuring that corrective actions (if any) are implemented;
- Issuing progress reports as specified in WP7;
- Monitoring the activities of the project;
- Coordinating the overall operational activities of the project; and
- Any other management activities.
- Meetings will, whenever possible, be synchronised with project events, such as conferences and/or workshops, in order to minimise travel costs.

5.1.5 TECHNICAL MANAGEMENT

The Project Coordinator (Luis Romeral), and the Work Package Leaders (WPL), along with a Scientific and Technical Committee (STC) will provide all the necessary guidance towards scientific and technical orientations and development in the project. Furthermore, Dissemination and Exploitation managers will provide support for any business-related, communication and dissemination issues.

The WP Leaders (WP1 to WP7) will undertake the management of the RHODaS project, under the supervision of the COO and PEB. The Work-Package Leaders within the PEB have the following functions: communicate plans, deliverables, documents and information connected with the Work Package, Work-Package implementation plan and advise Project Executive Board of any proposed updates to the Consortium Plan, day-to-day coordination on project progress with respect to technical work within the Work-Package, follow up decisions arrived at by Consortium Bodies insofar as they affect the Work-Package, and advise the Project Coordinator of any discrepancy with the Consortium Plan, including any delay in delivery. The activities the Work Package Leaders have to supervise have been described in the project work plan section.

The responsibilities of the Work-Package Leaders will include:

- Organisation of the work-package activities;
- Promotion of the consensus from WP members on the actual activities' plan;
- Coordination of, and contribution to, the reporting activities, by issuing a proposed Table of Contents (TOC) to the WP members, highlighting the different responsibilities (consistent with the Description of Work) and by incorporating members' suggestions as appropriate;
- Identification of possible critical or conflict areas; and,
- Contribute to the updating of the risk assessment table (relate to table further in the proposal).

Any dispute between the W-Package Leaders will be resolved by reference to the STC (in case of scientific /technological disagreement), and to the PEB. The WP leader is ultimately responsible for achieving the WP objectives, and shall use all the required endeavour and management tools foreseen in the project management structure to reach the targets.

The appointed leaders of each of the individual tasks will be responsible for the appropriate application and management of resources to ensure that the deliverables are delivered on time, to budget, and are of a suitably high quality.

5.1.6 COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION MANAGERS

The Communication and Dissemination Manager, CDM, (KNEIA) will contribute developing and managing the dissemination strategy, monitoring the results and establishing contacts with other relevant projects. Moreover, the Communication and Dissemination Manager will be in charge for the organization of Workshops, conferences, training sessions and other events relevant to project promotion.

A Communication Plan will be drawn up to disseminate the results from the project. Communication activities include publication of research results (in accordance with the outlines of the STC), presentation at conferences, events and trade shows, activities engaging with the general public, dedicated dissemination events, on-line (website, newsletters and e-bulletins, social media, etc.) and of-line (leaflets, factsheets, etc.) dissemination.

The Exploitation Manager, EM, (VALEO) is the responsible of exploitation strategy and will manage the promotion of the solutions developed during the project. The EM will look for potential stakeholders and investors, interested in the project results, and will be constantly in contact with the public administration, to promote follow-up activities, along with the CDM according to the scenario. In charge for knowledge management and

Intellectual Property Rights, the EM will be available for discussions regarding IPR with the partners at any time during the project. To avoid the creation of conflicts with regard to rights of use and commercialisation of certain IPR arising from the project, the partners will, during the negotiation of the grant agreement, conduct due diligence to determine whether any partner has pre-existing obligations with respect to specific IPR. Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) is a major management issue in the exploitation and dissemination of scientific project results.

The management of IPR will involve:

- Identification of patentable research findings;
- Evaluation of whether to file for IPR protection or not;
- Preparation of applications for IPR protection;
- Determination of the rights of use for each single exploitable result of the RHODaS solution;
- Exploitation of the IPR generated by the partners.

Key Exploitable Results, KER, of RHODaS have been defined, and potential end users identified, as described in Table 6.

Table 6. RHODaS Key exploitable results

KERs	Proposed IPR tool	Owners	Potential end users
KER 1: Innovative electric IMD Powertrain	Trademark	VAL, VS, AIT	Automotive manufacturing, OEMs
KER 2: High power/high efficiency traction power converters	Patent	AIT, UPC, AU	Automotive component manufacturers and electric powertrain system integrators.
KER 3: Intelligent active gate drivers	Patent	UPC, AIT	Power converter manufacturers for energy conversion and management, storage systems, motor drives, etc.
KER 4: High voltage/high power traction motor	Patent, Trademark	VS	Automotive manufacturing, OEMs
KER 5: Digital twins of electric powertrains for holistic modelling and simulation	Copyright	NION	Automotive manufacturing, distributors and service providers companies

KNEIA will draw up a Plan for the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication activities (PDEC, D6.3), to mobilise stakeholders' interests and secure their support to the project. The purpose of the PDEC, which includes the Communication Plan, is to provide a formal planning document for using, communicating and disseminating knowledge throughout the project, and to ensure that as many stakeholders as possible have access to these results, with the aim of ensuring a high visibility of the funded actions and help to maximise the impact and the future exploitation of RHODaS results.

The PDEC will define: the purpose of the dissemination and communication actions; the message; the type of audience; the communication methods; the timing over the project execution. Performance indicators will be established as part of the plan, such as number

of citations, number of hits on web, number of downloads, number of industry consultations (from tradeshows/exhibitions), number of policy-maker engagements, etc.

Twice a year, the CDM and the EM will assemble an Innovation and Dissemination Meeting. Together, they will review the results generated by the project and update the PDEC.

In close agreement with the STC and the PCT, the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Managers will actively look to contribute to the standards and policies. With this aim, project results will be reviewed and analyse its potential contribution towards regulations and standard developments and applicable policy revision in project field. In this regard, cooperation with regulatory bodies (CEN/CENELEC) and third-party sales and distribution licensees in project field will be implemented.

5.1.7 ADVISORY BOARD

An industry and academy-driven Industrial Advisory Board (IAB), integrated by relevant researchers and stakeholders of the entire supply chain has been established to provide support in the effective dissemination and exploitation of the outcomes from the RHODaS Project. This advisory board will have an external role and will assess the project's progress and deliverables. Also, the IAB will support the project implementation by highlighting the e-truck industrial sector technical and performance requirements in terms of power density, efficiency, cost and sustainability.

The Advisory Board is composed at the date of the KoM by academic members (Institute of Combustion Engines and Transport, Poznan University of Technology), material manufacturers (VisiC Technologies, GaN Systems Inc), OEMs (CHN Industrial, Volvo Trucks, Irizar) and Associations (IEA 4E PECTA, AEPIBAL, AEDIVE). New representatives from different industrial associations, companies and research bodies could be approached during the project execution.

A number of stakeholders have been already identified and contacted in the proposal preparation phase. The selected IAB members have expressed their will to spread among their networks the project results, to promote the uptake of the technologies developed in RHODaS. Below, some of them are listed:

- Professor Jerzy Merkisz (Head of the Division of Combustion Engines at Poznan UT and President of the Board of the Society of Combustion Engines)
- Tamara Baksht, CEO at VisiC Technologies
- Larry Spaziani, VP Global Sales at GaN Systems Inc.
- Leire Martín, Research Team Manager, Irizar e-mobility
- Luca Giovenzana, Chief Eng. Hybrid Powertrain at FPT Powertrain Technologies (CNH)
- Lars Martensson, Director Environment and Innovation at Volvo Trucks
- Roland Brüniger, Chair of the Power Electronic Conversion Technology Annex Program PECTA, Manager at Swiss Federal Office of Energy
- Luis Marquina, President of AEPIBAL

The IAB will be one of the most valuable communication routes with different target groups, and their resources and channels will be used to disseminate the results to the relevant industrial sectors and establish proper routes of exploitation. Furthermore, the Advisory Board will ensure that the project management is constantly informed of significant changes in the knowledge domains and markets underpinning the project activities.

The IAB will meet at least once a year (at the beginning: M3, mid-way through: M18 and at the end: M36) to follow-up on the project results and provide technical support and commercial guidance. Meetings will be coordinated by the PCT, and the EM and CDM. Other meetings could be agreed with the PCT and/or Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Managers to review and discuss particular project results and industrial trends.

5.2 QUALITY ASSURANCE PLAN (QAP) & PEER REVIEWING

A Quality Assurance Plan (QAP) will be developed and proposed by the PCT, in coordination with the PEB. The plan is supposed to function as an operational manual for the consortium, identifying any unambiguous and appropriate workflow between consortium partners and the various roles, designed for the project. The PC, with support from the STC, will be the responsible of updating the QAP. The QAP will be part of the D7.2 Project Management Handbook (M3, Responsible: UPC), in which the communication flow and methods to guarantee the quality of the project and the outcomes during its execution, as well as to ensure the proper management of the project, are described.

Also, QAP will consider actions and suggestions described in the deliverable D7.5 Gender Action Plan and Ethics considerations (M6, Responsible: UPC), in which a framework for assessing the various ethical issues related to the development, design, and the need and importance of promoting gender balance and equality transversely and how the ethics considerations are fulfilled throughout the project planning and implementation, are described.

QAP will identify the following:

- A clear list of all review, audit and acceptance points in the lifecycle of the project.
- A list of internal reviewers and review criteria for each key deliverable.
- All types of forms and other documents that must be prepared in the project course, in order to closely track the progress and allow for early problem identification and solving, and people involved.
- Risks and contingency plans.
- Research data that will be available in Open Access. All the research data will be of the highest quality, have long-term validity and will be well documented in order other researchers to be able to get access and use them after 5 years Quality control of the data is the responsibility of the relevant responsible partner generating the data.

RHODaS will adopt a peer-review process to assist the task leaders with ensuring the high quality of the project deliverables, which is described below.

- A preliminary table of content should be sent by the responsible partner to the WPL and the PCT at least 2 months in advance of the delivery date.
- A complete deliverable version should be sent to the WP Leader at least 2-3 weeks before the delivery date. The WP leader will be responsible for completing the first peer review of the work and may request that the partners in question rework the deliverable when necessary.
- The reviewed document should be sent to the COO/PCT at least 2 week weeks before the delivery date for a final peer review. The PCT is responsible for

achieving the required quality in all deliverables and milestones submitted to the EU Project Officer.

The procedure for document Quality Assurance (QA) is defined as follows:

- *Status Draft* is achieved when the primary author of a deliverable has defined the Table of Content of the document, which is then ready to be sent to other contributors with preferably explicit information of what type of contribution and where in the document.
- *Status Working Document* is achieved when the initial, primary author of a deliverable has reviewed the document and approved it internally and makes it available to other partners for comments.
- *Status Released* is achieved when the edition process is finished and the document is ready to be reviewed by project partners (other than the document editor and authors) and / or peer-reviewers.
- *Status Delivered* is achieved when a deliverable is approved by the PCTSTC and given to the PC for submission to the European Commission. The issuing date is that of the approval by the SC.
- *Status Approved* by the EC is when the EC has approved and accepted the deliverable.

The final draft of main deliverables may be sent (for those not public, under confidentiality restriction) to some of the key experts within the Industrial Advisory Group to undertake a peer review of the work. The feedback from this peer review process will be incorporated into the final deliverable, thus ensuring that it is of a suitably high quality, addresses the relevant target audience, is written clearly and is well presented. The peer-review reports and the final content of each deliverable will be reviewed by the PEB to ensure that appropriate peer review recommendations are adopted. As a part of the documentation QA, the following levels of documents would apply and should be clearly labelled by the WP leader, responsible for the deliverable documentation:

- PU: Public.
- PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission services).
- RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission services).
- CO: Confidential

5.3 PROJECT MEETINGS STRUCTURE

The key meetings to be held during the project term are listed in Table 7. Meetings will play an important role in the scientific and technical project management as well as in the communication strategy and knowledge transfer within the consortium. For the Periodic Review Meetings at M18, M36 and M42, the PCT (UPC and NION) are also responsible for preparation of the periodic and final reports by the specified deadlines, with the mandatory participation of all the partners, and specially, the WPLs. Meetings can be face-to-face or hybrid, combining remote and local assistance, or fully online, at the discretion of the calling partner. In any case, the quorum must be equal to or greater than 2/3 in order to hold the meeting.

Table 7 – Project meetings and locations

Meeting	Date	Location	Organizer
Kick off Meeting	M0	Barcelona, Spain	UPC
6 months consortium meeting	M6	Seibersdorf/Vienna, Austria	AIT
12 months consortium meeting	M12	Bielsko-Biała/Krakow, Poland	BOSMAL
18 months consortium meeting	M18	Barcelona, Spain	UPC
24 months consortium meeting	M24	Aarhus, Denmark	AU
30 months consortium meeting	M30	Amiens, France	VALEO
36 months consortium meeting	M36	Erlangen/Nürnberg, Germany	VALEO SIEMENS
42 months consortium meeting	M42	Brussels, Belgium	UPC

Note: The meeting locations are only proposal and are subject to discussion and agreement between project partners. 18m 36 and 42 months meetings correspond to the Official Reporting Periods, in which a Periodic Report must be submitted to the EC.

In summary, the following technical and committees meetings' frequency is foreseen:

- Periodic Reporting Meetings, at M18, M36 and M42
- GA meetings, at M6, M12, M18, M24; M30, M36, M42.
- Project Executive Board, PEB, regular bi-monthly meetings (at least) coordinated by the COO and the PCT. PEB can be requested by any of the partners' representatives at any time.
- Monthly telephone conference meetings will be organised by the WP leaders for all work packages using appropriate and convenient tools for conference calling (Goto, Skype, CISCO, Adobe Connect etc.). These meetings will enable project partners to raise any technical and administrative issues regarding individual work packages and give an opportunity to the work package leaders to update partners on progress.
- Scientific and Technical Committee, SCT, technical meetings every 3 months through a virtual platform with the participation of the Work-Package leaders and the PCT.
- Innovation and Dissemination Meeting, twice a year, coordinated by the CDM and the EM
- Industrial Advisory Board meetings, at least once a year (at the beginning: M3, mid-way through: M18 and at the end: M36). Meetings will be coordinated by the PCT, and the EM and CDM. Other meetings could be agreed with the PCT and/or Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Managers at any time.

5.4 DECISION-MAKING

In terms of Decision-making mechanisms, the following procedures will apply:

- Regular way-of-working

At the highest level, the PEB will provide a forum for discussion and will decide on management issues. Decisions of the PEB are binding for the project. The PEB will decide on major modifications of the overall work plan, possible addition of new partners, and will prepare requests for amendments to the European Commission. UPC will chair the PEB. The PEB serves as an advisory and overall monitoring forum for RHODaS and holds a decision-making role when it would come to a disagreement in the project. Day-to-day decisions at the technical level will be made by the WPLs, where needed after consultation of the COO.

- Problem handling

The philosophy of the Consortium regarding problem handling and corrective actions is in the first place based on prevention. In case a problem arises, it will be tackled as soon as possible and at the lowest possible level, meanwhile bringing the problem and the proposed solution to the immediate attention of the COO. Each partner of the consortium is responsible for the execution of any part of its share of the project and for fulfilling other European Commission contractual obligations. However, in case, that a partner performs poorly, due to technical and/or resource reasons, this will be promptly documented in project meeting minutes. The COO will try to solve the problem immediately by all possible means thus limiting the impact for the project.

In case the problem will not be resolved at the lower level, a meeting of the PEB will then be organised on short notice. The PEB will either solve the problem or decide on the final corrective actions, which may be banning the partner from the project. All actions will be properly documented, and the procedures will be aligned with the current recommendations of European Commission policy.

6. COMMUNICATION

Communication within the RHODaS project is achieved across a number of platforms: project website, internal communication platform, video/tele conferencing, email, social networking (Twitter, Slideshare, LinkedIn, Youtube) and face-to-face meetings.

Alternatives for **video calling and online conferencing** tools include Cisco Webex, Microsoft Teams, GoToMeeting, Google Meet, Jitsi Meet and many more. The final selection for the RHODaS project will consider the tool availability and the support that the Coordinator (UPC) can provide, and of course, the acceptance of the partners.

For WPs technical meetings, project partners are free to choose from a wide range of free and paid conferencing calling software including but not limited to all the previous described, such as for instance Skype, Adobe Connect and other VoIP providers. WP leaders should ensure that for each work package conference calls, there is enough time and provision to organise a convenient mode of teleconferencing for all project partners.

Partners will use a **software repository throughout the project** to share information, plan events, discuss grants, and communicate about the project. The repository must ensure to follow European project management guidelines for security and GDPR (European General Data Protection Requirements) compliance. GDPR requires that data cannot be stored in or transferred through countries outside the European Economic Area that do not have equivalently strong data protection standards (it should be noted that the United States is not currently compliant with GDPR requirements). Therefore, only project management tools based and hosted in Europe can guarantee full GDPR compliance. Solutions for this repository with full GDPR compliance could be EMDESK or ownCloud, for example. Once again, the final selection of the RHODaS project will consider the technical support that UPC can provide and the interests of the partners.

For the multidisciplinary **open repository for storing datasets**, papers, and other research materials, the Zenodo server and search engine is the primary choice.

Zenodo allows you to upload data in any file format, automatically assigning a digital object identifier (DOI) to all Zenodo files, and of course, Zenodo is compliant with the data management requirements of Horizon Europe, the ERC and other EU research and innovation funding programmes.

Finally, a **RHODaS website** will be developed and maintained during project execution and beyond, which will include all kinds of public information about the project, activities, results and impacts. The website will also have a private folder for use by RHODaS partners

Full description of the Communication channels will be included in Deliverable D7.2, Project Management Handbook (M3, Responsible, UPC)

6.1 PARTNER CONTACT DETAILS

Typically, there is more than one contact per beneficiary; however, Table 8 provides the main for contact for each Party in accordance with Section A2.4 of the Grant Agreement Preparation Form (GAP).

Table 8 – Main partner contacts

Partner	City	Country	Contact name	Email
UPC	Barcelona	Spain	Luis Romeral	luis.romeral@upc.edu
KNEIA	Barcelona	Spain	Cristina Barragan	cbarragan@kneia.com
TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF VIENNA	Vienna	Austria	Rainer Pamminger	rainer.pamminger@tuwien.ac.at
AARHUS UNIVERSITY	Aarhus	Denmark	Corneliu Barbu	coba@ece.au.dk
AUSTRIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY	Seibersdorf/ Vienna	Austria	Peter Scheuermann	peter.scheuermann@ait.ac.at
BOSMAL	Bielsko-Biala	Poland	Piotr Bielaczyc	piotr.bielaczyc@bosmal.com.pl
VALEO-EMBAYAGES	Amiens	France	Christophe Verdoucq	christophe.verdoucq@valeo.com
VAELO-SIEMENS	Erlangen	Germany	Sebastian Waider	sebastian.waider.jv@valeo-siemens.com
NVISION	Barcelona	Spain	Jose Sáez	jose.saez@nvision.es

7. CONCLUSION

This report has provided a brief review of the KoM meeting RHODaS project, objectives, deliverables and milestones, as well as a system of project organisation.

The KoM meeting agenda, discussions, presentations and other graphic information was provided in Chapter 2. RHODaS project objectives and impact was described in Chapter 3.

A work-plan providing a flow of work detailing the requisite Deliverables, Milestones and schedules was provided in Chapter 4. To manage the sequence of work as seamlessly as possible, Chapter 5 provided a management structure detailing the governance of the RHODaS consortium with respect to the various committees set-up and agreed by the project partners (as detailed in the Consortium Agreement). The Chapter included information on the Scientific and Technical Committee and the Innovation and Dissemination managers. Chapter 5 provides a first approach to the information on the channels of communication to ensure smooth information flow and updates.

This document lays out a comprehensive framework of the main project objectives and the governance structure to realise the full project potential (as described in the EC-Grant Agreement).